

The "Nuke Mars" Proposition for Terraforming: Simulating Radiological Contamination and Hazards

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Abstract

Background: Conceptual proposals to use nuclear detonations as a rapid means of terraforming Mars seldom quantify the radiological risks such events would impose on future surface settlements. Understanding fallout behaviour in the Martian environment is essential for evaluating the safety of prospective colonies. **Materials and Methods:** A Mars-specific Monte Carlo fallout model was developed for a representative 100-kt, fission-dominated atmospheric detonation. The model simulates particle-scale transport and deposition in a low-pressure CO₂ atmosphere, estimates area-averaged contamination (Bq m⁻²) over a circular colony footprint located downwind, and converts the resulting time-dependent external dose into expected loss of life expectancy (life years lost). Multiple shielding configurations, including regolith, concrete, and lead were evaluated to quantify dose attenuation. **Results and Discussion:** For the selected source term, mean deposited activities over 1,000 days were approximately 10⁴ Bq m⁻² for Cs-137 and Sr-90, 10⁴–10⁵ Bq m⁻² for Ru-106 and Ce-144, and 10⁷ Bq m⁻² for Ba-140. These contamination levels correspond to an unshielded life-expectancy loss of roughly 0.1 years per colonist. Shielding reduced risk exponentially: meter-scale regolith coverage or decimetre-scale concrete walls were sufficient to lower life-years-lost to effectively negligible values. These findings indicate that while fallout from nuclear terraforming detonations could pose a substantial hazard to unprotected settlements, the shielding already envisioned for cosmic-ray mitigation provides robust protection against such fallout. **Conclusion:** The study demonstrates that nuclear-driven terraforming concepts must account for radiological fallout risks to surface habitats. Although unshielded colonies would face significant exposure, appropriately engineered settlements can reduce long-term health impacts to minimal levels. Integrating fallout modelling into mission architecture and planetary-engineering policy discussions is therefore essential for responsible planning of future Martian habitation.

Keywords: Mars, Nuclear Fallout, Radiological Protection, Anthropogenic Isotopes, Human Colonization of Mars.

2. Introduction

Terraforming Mars has been in human imagination since the 19th century. Due to water ice present on its surface and possible subsurface water makes it a suitable candidate for human colonization [1]. Different proposals and suggestions to terraform Mars by using nuclear detonations in Martian atmosphere or over its poles have been discussed and this idea has been popularized by Elon Musk [2]. This ‘jump start’ terraforming strategy emphasizes on rapid evaporation of polar volatiles resulting in atmospheric thickening and enhanced warming of the surface through the greenhouse effect [3] but often overlooked fact is the radiological consequences of detonating nuclear weapons in the Martian atmosphere. These detonations will produce unstable fission products which will be deposited eventually on the ground and will stay there for a long time as studies suggest the same for Nuclear detonations on earth [4], [5]. This radioactive fallout would be a huge hindrance in establishing a human colony on Mars and could increase the mission costs by trillions of dollars, just to protect the astronauts from the radiation emitted by these fission products. In addition to direct external exposure from ground deposited radionuclides, such scenarios raise concerns about resuspension of contaminated dust, activation of local infrastructure, and long-term constraints on agriculture, water use, and surface operations in and around a Mars colony.

Mars differs fundamentally from Earth in surface pressure, atmospheric density, composition, and gravity, and these properties strongly affect plume rise, particle transport, and deposition patterns [6]. Present day Mars is characterized by a cold, low-density carbon-dioxide atmosphere with mean near-surface pressures of order 6 mbar, typical temperatures near 210 K, and characteristic densities around $0.02 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ under gravitational acceleration $3.71 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$, values that are only small fractions of their terrestrial counterparts [7]. These conditions weaken buoyant cloud rise, alter drag and gravitational settling velocities, and modify resuspension behaviour relative to Earth, so that terrestrial fallout models cannot be applied directly without substantial modification. The same low pressure that allows particles to fall with relatively high terminal velocities also implies large Knudsen numbers for small aerosols, requiring slip-flow corrections and careful treatment of non-continuum effects in any fallout calculation [8], [9]. Moreover, Martian boundary-layer flows are shaped by strong diurnal thermal tides, dust devils, katabatic winds, and frequent dust storms, which together create a transport environment very different from the midlatitude westerlies typically assumed in Earth based fallout models [10], [11], [12].

Existing Mars radiation studies focus mainly on galactic cosmic rays and solar energetic particles as the primary drivers of long-term dose to astronauts and putative microbial life, with particular attention to shielding requirements for surface habitats, subsurface ice stability, and biosignature preservation [13], [14].

These works generally treat the radiation field as spatially diffuse and temporally variable but do not consider highly localized, anthropogenic sources (For obvious reasons) such as fission product fallout from nuclear devices.

From a mission-design perspective, the question is not only whether fallout from a single detonation poses an unacceptable risk to a given settlement, but also how risk scales with yield, burst altitude, distance, and the number of devices, as well as what mitigation measures, such as siting, shielding, or operational constraints are required to maintain doses within acceptable limits. Because Mars exploration architectures increasingly envision permanent or semi-permanent colonies with industrial-scale in-situ resource utilization, some form of agriculture and human populations [15], [16], even modest increases in lifetime cancer risk or constraints on habitable land area can have outsized ethical and policy implications. These issues are magnified by the fact that Mars is portrayed in public discourse as a “backup planet” for humanity; radiological contamination from large scale nuclear activities could undermine that narrative by rendering prime settlement regions uninhabitable due to contamination.

This work addresses these gaps by constructing a Mars-specific Monte Carlo fallout model for a single representative 100 kilo-tons fission-dominated atmospheric detonation and applying it to a hypothetical surface colony located several kilometres downwind. The model tracks an ensemble of equal activity fallout particles that carry a specified set of key fission products, computes their deposition in $\text{Bq}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$, and derives area-averaged contamination over a circular colony footprint. Time-dependent external dose from deposited radionuclides is converted into a committed effective dose and exponential attenuation is used to represent regolith, concrete, and lead shielding of varying thicknesses, consistent with standard external exposure formalisms. The shielded committed dose is then mapped to an expected loss of life expectancy, expressed in life years lost per person, using a nominal risk-per-sievert coefficient and an average life-years lost per radiation-induced fatality. This work thereby provides a quantitative basis for judging whether atmospheric nuclear detonations for terraforming are compatible with acceptable radiological risk for human settlements on Mars.

3. Methodology

3.1. Model Setup

The detonation is idealized as a pure-fission device with yield $Y = 100$ kt (TNT equivalent). The total energy release is

$$E_{\text{tot}} = Y E_{\text{kt}} \quad (1)$$

Where,

$$E_{\text{kt}} = 4.184 \times 10^{12} \text{ J kt}^{-1} \quad (2)$$

is the conventional energy per kiloton of TNT.

Assuming an average energy per fission

$$E_f = 200 \times 10^6 \text{ eV} \times 1.6022 \times 10^{-19} \text{ J eV}^{-1},$$

the total number of fissions is

$$N_f = \frac{E_{\text{tot}}}{E_f} = \frac{Y E_{\text{kt}}}{E_f} \quad (3)$$

For each primary fission product i with independent fission yield y_i (atoms per fission), the initial number of atoms and decay constant are

$$N_{i,0} = y_i N_f \quad (4)$$

$$\lambda_i = \frac{\ln 2}{T_{1/2,i}} \quad (5)$$

where $T_{1/2,i}$ is the physical half-life (s). The corresponding initial activity is

$$A_{i,0} = \lambda_i N_{i,0} \quad (6)$$

The explicit isotope set includes Cs-137, Sr-90, I-131, Ru-106, Ce-144, and Ba-140, together with short-lived daughters that shape early-time decay chains but have zero initial yield [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22].

3.2. Martian atmosphere and plume initialization

The Martian atmosphere is represented as a vertically uniform CO_2 gas with density ρ_a , dynamic viscosity μ_a , temperature $T = 210$ K, and gravitational acceleration $g_M = 3.71 \text{ m s}^{-2}$. A representative near-surface pressure P of 0.00628 atm is considered [23]. The molecular mean free path Λ for CO_2 is estimated as

$$\Lambda = \frac{k_B T}{\sqrt{2} \pi d^2 P} \quad (7)$$

where k_B is Boltzmann's constant and d is an effective CO_2 molecular diameter [24].

The stabilized cloud top height is parameterized as

$$H_{\text{stab}} = \alpha Y^{1/3} \quad (8)$$

where α is a calibration factor chosen to represent plausible cloud rise under present day Martian conditions. Individual particle release heights $z_{0,j}$ are drawn from a truncated normal distribution:

$$z_{0,j} = \mathcal{N}(\mu_z, \sigma_z^2) \quad (9)$$

With,

$$\mu_z = \beta H_{\text{stab}} \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma_z = \gamma H_{\text{stab}} \quad (11)$$

subject to the constraint

$$z_{0,j} \geq z_{\text{min}} \quad (12)$$

where β , γ , and z_{min} control the vertical spread and minimum injection altitude.

A constant horizontal wind U is imposed along the downwind x direction, with no mean cross wind component.

3.3. Particle sizes and terminal settling

Fallout is represented by N_p spherical particles, each carrying an equal share of each nuclide's initial activity. Particle radii r_j are sampled from a lognormal distribution with activity median aerodynamic diameter d_{AMAD} and geometric standard deviation GSD:

$$f(r) = \frac{1}{r \sigma_r \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp \left(-\frac{(\ln r - \mu_r)^2}{2\sigma_r^2} \right) \quad (13)$$

Where,

$$\mu_r = \ln \left(\frac{d_{\text{AMAD}}}{2} \right), \sigma_r = \ln(\text{GSD}) \quad (14)$$

And AMAD is Activity Median Aerodynamic Diameter. For a particle (Perfect sphere) of radius r and density ρ_p , the volume and projected area are

$$V_p = \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 \quad (15)$$

$$A_p = \pi r^2 \quad (16)$$

Rarefaction Effects occur when a gas's mean free path approaches or exceeds the size of a particle, which occurs in Mars' very thin, low-pressure atmosphere. The Cunningham slip correction factor alters the traditional Stokes' Law drag force calculation because the no-slip condition (fluid velocity equals zero at the particle surface) is no longer applicable. This correction factor minimizes the projected drag force as the particle 'slips' between the widely spaced gas molecules, allowing it to move faster than expected by classical continuum fluid dynamics. Hence, the Rarefaction effects in the low pressure Martian atmosphere are incorporated using the Cunningham slip correction,

$$C_c(r) = 1 + \text{Kn} \left[A + B \exp \left(-\frac{C}{\text{Kn}} \right) \right] \quad (17)$$

with

$$\text{Kn} = \frac{\Lambda}{r} \quad (18)$$

where A , B , and C are empirical constants and Kn is the Knudsen number [25].

The Reynolds number is

$$Re = \frac{2rv\rho_a}{\mu_a} \quad (19)$$

and the drag coefficient $C_D(Re)$ is specified piecewise so as to recover Stokes flow at low Re , an empirical correlation at intermediate Re , and a constant high- Re limit [26], [27].

At terminal settling, the vertical force balance is

$$(\rho_p - \rho_a)g_M V_p = \frac{1}{2} C_D \rho_a A_p v_t^2 \quad (20)$$

which is solved iteratively for the terminal velocity v_t , using a slip-corrected Stokes estimate as the initial guess and updating C_D until convergence. Values of $v_t(r)$ are precomputed on a radius grid and interpolated during the Monte Carlo transport.

3.4. Monte Carlo transport and surface deposition

Given the release height $z_{0,j}$ and terminal velocity $v_{t,j}$ of particle j , the settling time is

$$t_{s,j} = \frac{z_{0,j}}{v_{t,j}} \quad (21)$$

Downwind advection in the imposed wind field yields a horizontal distance

$$x_j = U t_{s,j} \quad (22)$$

Cross-wind dispersion is represented by a Gaussian displacement,

$$y_j = \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_y^2) \quad (23)$$

with

$$\sigma_y = \sigma_0 + \kappa \max(t_{s,j}, 0) \quad (24)$$

where σ_0 and κ parameterize, initial cloud spread and effective turbulent diffusion intensity.

The computational domain is discretised into Cartesian bins $\{x_k\}$ and $\{y_\ell\}$ of widths Δx and Δy , so that each grid cell has area

$$\Delta A = \Delta x \Delta y \quad (25)$$

For isotope i , each particle carries an equal activity parcel

$$a_{i,parcel} = \frac{A_{i,0}}{N_p} \quad (26)$$

If particle j falls into cell (k, ℓ) , the cell-integrated activity is updated as

$$A_{i,k\ell}^{cell} \leftarrow A_{i,k\ell}^{cell} + a_{i,parcel} \quad (27)$$

The areal activity density in that cell is

$$\tilde{A}_{i,k\ell} = \frac{A_{i,k\ell}^{cell}}{\Delta A} [\text{Bq m}^{-2}] \quad (28)$$

The total deposited activity from all isotopes is

$$\tilde{A}_{tot,k\ell} = \sum_i \tilde{A}_{i,k\ell} \quad (29)$$

3.5. Hypothetical Colony footprint and area-averaged contamination

A circular colony of radius R_c is centered at (x_c, y_c) along the downwind axis. Grid cell centers (x_k^c, y_ℓ^c) are defined as midpoints of each cell. A cell lies within the colony footprint if

$$(x_k^c - x_c)^2 + (y_\ell^c - y_c)^2 \leq R_c^2 \quad (30)$$

Let \mathcal{C} denote the set of index pairs (k, ℓ) satisfying this condition. For isotope i , the area-averaged initial colony deposition is

$$\bar{A}_{i,0}^{col} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{C}|} \sum_{(k,\ell) \in \mathcal{C}} \tilde{A}_{i,k\ell} \quad (31)$$

If $|\mathcal{C}| = 0$ (for example, very small R_c or coarse grid), the nearest cell to (x_c, y_c) is used as a fallback to define $\bar{A}_{i,0}^{col}$.

Assuming only physical decay after deposition, the time-dependent colony surface activity is

$$\bar{A}_i^{col}(t) = \bar{A}_{i,0}^{col} e^{-\lambda t} \quad (32)$$

These $\bar{A}_{i,0}^{col}$ values (in Bq m^{-2}) are the initial conditions for dose calculations.

Table 1 Various parameters used for fission products.

Isotope	yield	Half Life (days)	λ	Atoms initial (N_0)
Cs-137	0.065	11019	7.28025E-10	8.4872E+23
Sr-90	0.059	10515	7.62921E-10	7.70377E+23
I-131	0.0288	0.021	0.000365366	3.76048E+23
Ru-106	0.00402	371.8	2.15776E-08	5.24901E+22
Ce-144	0.0526	284.9	2.81591E-08	6.86811E+23
Ba-140	0.0612	12.75	6.29219E-07	7.99103E+23

3.6. External dose from deposited activity

The deposited activity is assumed to be uniformly mixed into a topsoil layer of thickness h_m and bulk density ρ_s . The soil mass per unit area is

$$M_s = \rho_s h_m [\text{kg m}^{-2}].$$

The corresponding activity concentration in soil is

$$C_i^{soil}(t) = \frac{\bar{A}_i^{col}(t)}{M_s} [\text{Bq kg}^{-1}] \quad (33)$$

Isotope-specific external dose-rate coefficients k_i^{ext} yield the dose-rate contribution

$$\dot{E}_i^{ext}(t) = k_i^{ext} C_i^{soil}(t) \quad (34)$$

The total external dose rate is

$$\dot{E}_{\text{ext}}(t) = \sum_i \dot{E}_i^{\text{ext}}(t) \quad (35)$$

After conversion to sieverts s^{-1} , the unshielded committed external dose over a time horizon $[0, T]$ is obtained via the trapezoidal rule on a discrete time grid $\{t_n\}$ with spacing Δt :

$$E_{\text{ext}}^{\infty} = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \left[\frac{\dot{E}_{\text{ext}}(t_n) + \dot{E}_{\text{ext}}(t_{n+1})}{2} \right] \Delta t \quad (36)$$

3.7. Shielding and life-years lost

Shielding is modelled as exponential attenuation of the external dose through a planar barrier of thickness x made of material m (regolith, concrete, or lead). For material density ρ_m and mass attenuation coefficient $(\mu/\rho)_m$ [28], the linear attenuation coefficient is

$$\mu_m = \left(\frac{\mu}{\rho} \right)_m \rho_m \quad (37)$$

The shielded committed external dose is

$$E_{\text{ext}}^{\infty, (m)}(x) = E_{\text{ext}}^{\infty} e^{-\mu_m x} \quad (38)$$

A nominal fatal cancer risk coefficient r (per Sv) and an average life-years lost per radiation-induced fatality L convert dose into expected loss of life expectancy. The probability of a radiation-induced fatal cancer at shield thickness x is approximated as

$$P_m(x) = r E_{\text{ext}}^{\infty, (m)}(x) \quad (39)$$

and the corresponding expected life-years lost is

$$\Delta L_m(x) = P_m(x) L = rL E_{\text{ext}}^{\infty} e^{-\mu_m x} \quad (40)$$

These quantities are evaluated for representative materials and thicknesses and reported in the Results as life-years lost per colonist. The mass attenuation results were compared with NIST-XCOM results for validity [29].

4. Results and Discussion

Over the 1000 day integration window, mean deposited activities at the colony (area-average over the circular footprint) are 1.27×10^4 Bq m^{-2} for Cs-137, 1.21×10^4 Bq m^{-2} for Sr-90, 2.33×10^4 Bq m^{-2} for Ru-106, 3.97×10^5 Bq m^{-2} for Ce-144, and 1.03×10^7 Bq m^{-2} for Ba-140, excluding I-131 because of its very short half-life and negligible contribution after the first weeks. The results are plotted in **Figure 1**.

4.1. Time evolution of deposited activity

Immediately after deposition (day 0), Ba-140 dominates the areal activity, with a colony-average of

1.03×10^7 Bq m^{-2} , more than an order of magnitude larger than Ce-144 (3.97×10^5 Bq m^{-2}) and roughly three orders of magnitude larger than any of the long lived nuclides (Cs-137 and Sr-90 each $\sim 1.2 \times 10^4$ Bq m^{-2}). Over the first 100 days, decay of Ba-140 reduces its activity by more than two orders of magnitude, from 1.03×10^7 to 4.50×10^4 Bq m^{-2} , while Ce-144 declines more modestly from 3.97×10^5 to 3.12×10^5 Bq m^{-2} ; during this interval, activities of Cs-137 and Sr-90 fall by less than 1% from their initial values.

Beyond 100 days, the very short-lived fraction of the inventory becomes negligible, and the time series approach the asymptotic behavior controlled by the half-lives of Ce-144, Ru-106, Sr-90, and Cs-137. By day 300, Ba-140 has been effectively removed from the inventory, with activity below 1 Bq m^{-2} , whereas Ce-144 remains at 1.92×10^5 Bq m^{-2} , about half of its initial value, and Ru-106 has decreased from 2.33×10^4 to 1.33×10^4 Bq m^{-2} . At the end of the 1000-day window, the short- and medium-lived nuclides have largely decayed (e.g., Ba-140 $\approx 2.5 \times 10^{-17}$ Bq m^{-2}), while Cs-137 and Sr-90 still retain more than 90% of their initial activity, with colony-averaged levels of 1.19×10^4 and 1.13×10^4 Bq m^{-2} , respectively.

4.2. Contribution of different isotopes to long-term contamination

The early-time dose field is controlled primarily by Ba-140 and Ce-144, which dominate the first few weeks to months due to their high initial activities, despite their shorter half-lives. Within the first 50 days, Ba-140 activity at the colony falls from 1.03×10^7 Bq m^{-2} to 6.82×10^5 Bq m^{-2} , while Ce-144 falls from 3.97×10^5 Bq m^{-2} to 3.52×10^5 Bq m^{-2} , so that the ratio of Ba-140 to Ce-144 shrinks from roughly 26:1 at day 0 to about 2:1 at day 50. Between 100 and 300 days, Ce-144 becomes the dominant contributor among the modelled isotopes, with activity declining from 3.12×10^5 to 1.92×10^5 Bq m^{-2} , while Ru-106 drops over the same period from 1.93×10^4 to 1.33×10^4 Bq m^{-2} .

On multi-year timescales, the contamination field transitions to one dominated almost entirely by Cs-137 and Sr-90, which change by less than 7% over 1000 days because of their long physical half-lives. At the 1000-day mark, Ce-144 activity has declined by nearly two orders of magnitude relative to its initial value, whereas Cs-137 and Sr-90 remain close to their initial values, implying that, for chronic exposure assessments beyond a few years, the long-lived Cs-137 and Sr-90 isotopes set the floor for residual external dose. In this scenario, the colony would therefore experience a short, intense phase of external dose dominated by Ba-140 and Ce-144, followed by a transition to a much lower but effectively persistent dose rate from Cs-137 and Sr-90.

Figure 1 Plotted decay rates of radioisotopes produced during the simulated fission process.

4.3. Life-years lost without shielding

For an unshielded colonist residing within the contaminated footprint, the integrated external dose over the modelled time horizon corresponds to an expected loss of life expectancy of 0.105 years (~40 days) for an exposure period of 1000 days. This metric aggregates contributions from all modelled isotopes and the full 1000day time series, folded through the external dose-rate coefficients and the assumed risk per sievert and life loss factors. In this configuration, the result is dominated by early-time exposure from Ba-140 and Ce-144, with Cs-137 and Sr-90 sustaining a small but non-zero contribution at later times because of their slowly decaying Bq m⁻² levels.

The loss of life in our results is relatively low mainly because of our three modelling choices to: the source term, the exposure pathway, and the shielding assumptions. In this work, a single 100 kt fission dominated detonation was modelled, not a multi megaton campaign or multiple repeated shots. The hypothetical colony is 90 km downwind, not directly under the burst or in the region of maximum near-field

dose, and the plume is spreading over a 2-D domain, so only a fraction of total activity lands on the colony footprint. Most of the very high initial Ba-140 and Ce-144 activity decays within months; once that's gone, the external dose rate is set by the much smaller but long-lived Cs-137 and Sr-90 inventories. The model includes external gamma exposure from ground contamination only. It does not include, inhalation of resuspended dust, ingestion through contaminated food or water, direct neutron/gamma dose from the prompt burst, or doses received during transit or outdoor work in less-shielded conditions. On Earth, post-accident health-impact studies show that inhalation and ingestion of iodine, Cs-137, and Sr-90 can be major contributors to lifetime risk, sometimes comparable to or larger than external dose, especially very near the source [30].

Extending the scenario from a single 100 kt detonation to a campaign of repeated or higher-yield blasts would amplify every element that currently keeps the risk moderate to low in the single-detonation case. Instead of one plume, multiple overlapping plumes would increase total deposited activity, enlarge the

contaminated area, and raise the probability that at least some shots place the colony closer to peak deposition, so that both early-time Ba-140/Ce-144 dose and long-term Cs-137/Sr-90 dose would scale upward, potentially by orders of magnitude. Because dose and thus life-years lost scale roughly linearly with integrated exposure in the low-to-moderate dose regime assumed in our model, a campaign of many detonations or higher cumulative yield could push the expected life-loss per colonist from the 0.1-year range into multi-year territory even before adding ingestion and inhalation pathways, making such a strategy clearly incompatible with contemporary radiological protection principles and any credible Mars settlement architecture.

4.4. Effect of regolith, concrete, and lead shielding

The dependence of life-years lost on wall thickness exhibits a simple exponential attenuation, but the material-specific attenuation coefficients produce large differences in required thickness to achieve a given level of risk reduction. For regolith shielding, life-years lost decrease from 0.105 years at zero thickness to 0.040 years at 0.10 m, 0.015 years at 0.20 m, and 5.9×10^{-3} years at 0.30 m, representing successive reductions of about 62%, 86%, and 94% relative to the unshielded case. By 0.50 m of regolith, the expected loss of life is reduced to 8.7×10^{-4} years, and at 1.0 m the value is 7.1×10^{-6} years, indicating that meter-scale regolith berms are sufficient to drive fallout-related life-loss to effectively negligible levels in this scenario.

Concrete, with a higher density and mass attenuation coefficient, yields similar risk reductions with substantially smaller thicknesses. A 0.10 m concrete wall lowers life-years lost from 0.105 to 2.43×10^{-2} years, and 0.20 m reduces this further to 5.63×10^{-3} years, both representing significantly stronger attenuation than equal-thickness regolith. At 0.30 m of concrete, life-years lost fall to 1.30×10^{-3} years, while 0.50 m gives 6.94×10^{-5} years; by 1.0 m, the expected loss is 4.57×10^{-8} years, effectively eliminating fallout-related external risk for practical purposes.

Lead, as expected, provides the most efficient shielding by mass, driving life-years lost down by many orders of magnitude with only centimeter scale thicknesses. At 0.05 m, lead already reduces life-years lost from 0.105 to 1.68×10^{-4} years, a reduction of roughly three orders of magnitude. A thickness of 0.10 m brings the expected loss to 2.68×10^{-7} years, and 0.20 m reduces it further to 6.81×10^{-13} years; beyond about 0.30 m, additional lead yields only marginal practical benefit because life-years lost have already fallen below 10^{-18} years.

These results show that, for the chosen source term and geometry, modest thicknesses of regolith (tens of centimetres) are sufficient to limit fallout-induced loss of life expectancy to well below 0.01 years, while concrete or lead can attain comparable protection with substantially less material, highlighting shielding design as a primary control on radiological risk from such a detonation.

Figure 2 Radiation shielding material efficacy for a Martian colony.

4.5. Fallout, chronic radiation, and habitat design

The modelled contamination field shows that unshielded colonists near a Martian detonation would incur a non-negligible loss of life expectancy (~0.1 life-years per person over 1000 days), driven first by short-lived Ba-140 and Ce-144 and later by long-lived Cs-137 and Sr-90. This exposure would come on top of the already elevated Martian radiation environment, where measurements and models indicate chronic surface dose rates of roughly 0.2–0.7 mSv per day (\approx 60–250 mSv per year), 10–50 times higher than typical natural background on Earth. In that context, fallout from a single detonation represents an acute perturbation superimposed on an intrinsically harsh baseline, reinforcing that any credible Mars settlement architecture must be radiation-hardened even if no nuclear devices are ever used.

The results also highlight that such hardening is technically achievable with relatively simple means. Tens of centimetres of regolith, emplaced as berms or overburden around and above pressurized volumes, cut fallout-related life-loss by more than an order of magnitude, while meter-scale thicknesses push risk into a regime that is small compared with routine cosmic-ray exposure over a multi-year surface stay. This is consistent with independent assessments that subsurface or heavily shielded habitats can reduce astronaut dose on Mars from several hundred mSv per year toward or below current career limits for space agencies. Because such shielding is also effective against galactic cosmic rays, solar particle events, micrometeorites, and dust storms, fallout protection can be treated as an additional benefit of design choices already motivated by other hazards.

4.6. Martian lava tubes as natural radiation shelters

Within this broader shielding strategy, Martian lava tubes and other subsurface voids emerge as particularly attractive locations for long term human bases. Remote sensing and comparative planetology studies suggest that lava tubes on Mars may be tens to hundreds of meters wide, with roofs that are tens of meters thick, providing natural overhead regolith cover far exceeding the thicknesses needed to reduce both cosmic-ray and fallout-induced dose to very low levels [31], [32]. Terrestrial and lunar analog measurements indicate that such structures can strongly attenuate ionizing radiation and micrometeorite fluxes and buffer interior temperatures against extreme diurnal swings, creating more stable microenvironments than the open surface and would act like natural ‘Nuclear Bunkers’ on Mars [33].

If a colony were sited within a lava tube, the many-meter-thick rock roof would act as an effective, passive shield against both the chronic Cosmic rays environment and any hypothetical fallout layer deposited on the surface above. In the context of the present fallout model, this configuration is roughly

equivalent to placing the habitat beneath multiple meters of high-density regolith, far more than is required to drive life lost from external exposure essentially to zero for the source term considered. While access, structural stability, and pressurization engineering would still pose major challenges, the combination of natural shielding, thermal stability, and protection from dust and micrometeorites has led multiple authors and space agencies to identify lava tubes as prime candidates for future Martian bases [34], [35].

4.7. Limits of nuclear terraforming and more feasible approaches

The fallout calculations also intersect with a broader body of work questioning the feasibility of using nuclear detonations as a terraforming tool. Proposals to detonate thermonuclear devices over the Martian poles aim to vaporize polar CO₂ and H₂O, thickening the atmosphere and driving greenhouse warming, but multiple analyses indicate that Mars does not possess enough readily accessible CO₂ to achieve Earth-like pressures or temperatures, even if all known surface and near-surface reservoirs were liberated [1], [36]. Moreover, the same dust and aerosol loading that would carry fission products downwind could also increase planetary albedo and induce a “nuclear winter” like cooling, counteracting any intended greenhouse effect. Combined with the localized radiological risk quantified here and the ethical, legal, and planetary protection issues associated with detonating nuclear weapons, these physical limits strongly argue against nuclear terraforming as a practical pathway for making Mars more Earth like.

More technically plausible approaches to incremental terraforming focus on targeted, long-duration interventions that enhance greenhouse forcing without catastrophic side effects, though even these remain speculative on human timescales. Proposed strategies include introducing synthetic, long-lived super-greenhouse gases (such as perfluorocarbons) into the atmosphere, deploying large orbital mirrors to increase insolation at selected regions, darkening surface ice or dust to reduce albedo, and pursuing extensive in-situ resource utilization and biosphere engineering within sealed habitats rather than attempting full planetary transformation [37]. Current analysis suggest that, given the limited accessible CO₂ and Mars weak gravity and lack of a magnetic field, any global terraforming effort would demand enormous energy and material inputs over centuries or longer and may still fall short of creating a stable, breathable atmosphere [38], [39]. Against this backdrop, the results of the present study reinforce a more conservative vision of Mars settlement: rather than trying to make the entire planet Earth-like via nuclear detonations, future efforts should focus on building deeply shielded, locally habitable oases, potentially in lava tubes or other subsurface structures.

5. Conclusion

A Mars-specific Monte Carlo fallout model for a 100 kt fission dominated atmospheric detonation shows that a nearby surface colony would experience an initial phase of intense external contamination dominated by Ba-140 and Ce-144, followed by a long-lived but much lower regime controlled by Cs-137 and Sr-90. Over 1000 days, the corresponding unshielded external exposure yields an expected loss of life expectancy of order 0.1 years per colonist, indicating that fallout is not negligible if settlements lack engineered protection. However, even modest shielding reduces this impact dramatically: tens of centimetres of regolith or concrete are sufficient to lower life-years lost below 0.01, and meter-scale structures or high Z materials such as lead render fallout related external risk effectively negligible. These results imply that any serious consideration of nuclear detonations for Mars terraforming must not be pursued and instead more realistic approaches should be taken under consideration.

Contribution

Mavia Anjum: Conceptualization, Data curation, Simulation, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing original draft, and Writing review & editing.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares that there are no financial, personal, or professional interests that could be perceived as influencing the research or the results presented in this manuscript. The author has no competing interests to disclose.

Data Availability Statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Ethical Statement

No animal or human subjects were used during this research.

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